

Women Entrepreneurship Issues and Challenges and Innovative Strategies

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Abstract

Despite developments made in gender equality, many gaps remain between males and females in realms such as education, employment and entrepreneurship. Beyond being a basic human right, women empowerment and gender equality is also a way to generate broad productivity gains. From a development perspective, empowering women and granting them equal rights in areas such as entrepreneurship and innovation has also positive spillover effects on key development outcomes. Women Entrepreneurs may be defined as the women or a group of women who initiate, organize and operate a business enterprise. The Government of India has defined women entrepreneurs as an enterprise owned and controlled by women generated in the enterprise to women. Like male entrepreneur's women entrepreneurs have many functions. They explore the prospects of starting a new enterprise; undertake risks, introduce new innovations, coordinate the administration work and control business. By providing effective leadership in all aspects of business *empowerment*, self-confidence and household responsibilities they strive towards the ultimate success of the enterprise. The centuries of subjugation and exploitation perpetuated on *women* by the patriarchal society have contributed to a large extent to low self-esteem among *women*. Women empowerment and through which achieving gender equality is essential for our society to ensure sustainable development of the country. Women Entrepreneur is a person who accepts this challenging role to meet her needs and become economically independent which is more supportive to face problems and challenges in the Society.

Keywords: Women entrepreneurs, Issues and Challenges, Innovations, Development

1. INTRODUCTION:

Women entrepreneurships are the process in which women initiates business by gathering all resources. This involves undertaking of risks, facing new challenges and thus makes way for providing employment to others and managing the business independently. Women entrepreneurs face a many problems right from the beginning till the end enterprise functions. It poses various problems to a woman entrepreneur. The problems of Indian women pertain to her responsibility towards family, society and work place. The tradition,

customs, socio cultural values, ethics, motherhood, work areas, feels of insecurity play a pivotal role in a women entrepreneur's life.

Women in rural areas have to suffer still further by facing tough resistance from men. The attitude of women entrepreneur towards society and constraints in which she has to live and work are not very conducive. "Men's" work and Women's work in the Indian traditional set up made a distinction between them, particularly that of the women with family responsibility. It curtailed the employment opportunity for women and in spite of this, number of women looking after business as a career have increased their thirst significantly over the past ten years to become a successful women entrepreneur. The changes in modern technology, globalization and acceleration in competition made the business world a more complex and dynamic one. These factors call for the importance of system thinking that it provides a framework for seeking interrelationships. Most of the Women Entrepreneurs in India are independently working with their own interest and ability. MSMEs (micro, small and medium enterprises) have played a vital role to enhance the participation of women in each and every setting and elevate their self confidence to handle any business. It was a world famous program to provide a basement for economic and personal growth among women. No wonder, India has also won the task by providing more opportunities and comfort in women. But still more women are selecting to be with their husband and child rather than to engage in an entrepreneurship area. This kind of activities is related with their affection towards their family rather than of the fact that they are facing any sort of restriction. If needed, a mass counseling can be done to overcome these problems. Generally, nowadays women are more passionate to do something through which they can earn their own income without asking money from their husband.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

1. Examination of the Issues and challenges of women entrepreneurs in India.
2. Suggestions related to improvement in Women entrepreneurs in India.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

This study is a descriptive one in nature. The secondary Data has been collected from Journals, Newspapers, various publications, economic survey reports, books, journals and periodicals and internet keeping in view with the present entrepreneurial aspects with regard to women entrepreneurs.

4. INDUSTRIES PROMOTED BY WOMEN ENTREPRENURES:

1. Agriculture
2. Incense stick Making
3. Papad Making
4. Tailoring (Embroidery and Designing)
5. Handicrafts
6. Catering Services and Fast Food Services
7. Running Restaurant, Snacks Bar etc.

8. Beauty Parlor
9. Cloth Shop
10. Online Shopping through What's App and Face book
11. Jewelry making
12. Clay modeling
13. Fashion designing and interior decoration

5. CATEGORISATION:

Women entrepreneurs it's broadly categorized into Three categories:-

◆ **Wealthy Entrepreneurs** – These are daughters and wives of wealthy businessmen. These women have the financial aid and the necessary resources to start a new enterprise and take business risks. As they have enough money in their hand, they are not much worried about the probable outcome. Because, they do not have the predisposition that if we lose money, we would become in poverty and we should be in cautious state all the time. People comes under this category are highly relaxed and they are even willing to take risk as well. Due to this relaxed attitude, most of the entrepreneurs are winners in their field.

◆ **Rural / Village Entrepreneurs** – These women belong to rural areas and choose a business suiting their resources and knowledge. Business carried out involves low investment, minimum risk and does not require any special skills. One of the main characteristics of rural entrepreneurs are they are not willing to take at least minor levels of risks. The main reason of this characteristics is, most of them belongs to poor family and may be the funding id dependent on loan or other informal ways. If they fail to win the particular job, they will be in utter poverty. So, this kind of thoughts may pull them back from taking any kind of risk in their business area.

◆ **Self-employed / Owner Entrepreneurs** – They are uneducated women who fall below the poverty line. They choose tiny and small enterprise which are convenient to manage and adequate for the sustenance of her family. People those who comes under this category are self sufficient to run their business. One of the main characteristics of this kind of entrepreneurship is the progress of their economic status would be very slow. In this category we can see a commonality in everyone's business. The reason is that, most of the work will be done by women. So they pick some convenient job of their own desire. Such as, papad making, pickle making, candle making, agarbathies, jewelry making, etc.

6. QUALITIES OF A WOMEN ENTREPRENUR:

6.1 Honesty and Strong:

Women entrepreneurs must possess honesty and strong in their workplace. This is one of the most important qualities of great leadership in business, because it builds valuable trust with people, from the employees and investors. Loyalty is one of the most important features in entrepreneurship. Without having a loyal and honest mind, nobody can grow into any kind of business for a long time. Whenever we deal with another entrepreneur, we need to create a strong and loyal personal connection with them and which may contribute in business growth.

6.2 Confident:

Confidence creates a sense that you know what you're doing. Confidence as the single most important trait needed for success and a confident woman can be a successful entrepreneur conquering the business world. It is important to follow one thing that whenever we deal with another entrepreneur it is necessary that we should not present our self with a lack of confidence state of mind. It will create a negative attitude. Even if you are not in confident in any particular area, and yet you are showing a confident attitude in front of others will create a positive outcome.

6.3 Resilience and persistence:

Entrepreneurship in a business field tough and full of uncertainties whether you are a male entrepreneur or female. By shouldering the heavier domestic and family responsibilities like childbirth and raising infants millions of women push through and succeed in building businesses due to resilience and dogged persistence. If you are a beginner in entrepreneurship it would be very difficult to adjust with family responsibilities and official or formal responsibilities. Dealing with both of this area, personal life and official life is somewhat difficult process in a beginning stage. So a better way should be created to deal with work- life harmony. An entrepreneur should consider one thing that their personal life should not interrupt with their professional life and their professional life should not interrupt with their personal life. One should give equal importance to both of this area.

6.4 Strength and Courage:

In a business world dominated by men female leaders require the strength and boldness to not only deal with new people and challenges, obstacles and setbacks, they keep taking risks, learn from their failures and fight for what they believe in success mantra. In a business setting formal behavior should be maintained. Any differentiation should not be kept on the basis of gender, sex, age, educational background or personal relationship.

6.5 Focus and Visuality:

In a world with constant distractions and endless demands, women leaders must know that success requires focus on what's most important to the business. Women entrepreneurs should be able to think strategically, prioritize goals and be responsible for achieving them, including by eliminating non-essential work that makes them non enthusiastic. The ability of goal setting should be improved if you are a beginner in entrepreneur field. An intense and updated focus is very essential to grow in the field of entrepreneurship. Without knowing the updating from their area, they cannot plan any new and progressive decision. So getting updated with new and popular concepts or trends is very essential.

6.6 Commitment to excellence:

When a women entrepreneur is excited and well aware of what she is doing, you have to go further towards development and deliver your products and services. Their offerings will be excellent or innovative, giving an edge against more complacent competitions.

6.7 Ability to Listen, Learn and Hard work:

Women entrepreneur should have a thorough knowledge about their customers, their industry and the product market. The best women entrepreneurs are curious for having new challenges faced by the business industry in the modern world. In today's modern world, everyone knows that success does not come without hard work. Successful women just do not work hard; they work hard all of the times. They are dedicated entrepreneurs marching towards the ultimate success of their own enterprise.

6.8 Communication skills:

Women entrepreneurs should cultivate and maintain a cordial relationship among their employees. They communicate and cultivate straightforwardness, confidentiality and by inspiring their subordinates thus building strong teamwork to enrich and achieve the company's goals.

6.9 Profit Earning and Utilizing Capacity:

Women Entrepreneurs they should follow have their own profit earning methods , they should follow the methods and systems of earnings. They have to focus the trend and taste of the society, which is always changes according to the environment.

6.10 Increases the Power of Entrepreneurs:

Especially Women Entrepreneur should attend the conferences, meetings, Video Conference etc. which increases the power and knowledge of the entrepreneur; it gives the Innovative solutions and methods to the entrepreneurs.

Fig.1: Shows the Qualities of Women Entrepreneur

7. ISSUES AND CHALLENGES OF WOMEN ENTREPRENEURSHIP:

Women entrepreneurship in India should strive for the uprooting the poverty to prosperity, total dependence to equality, agricultural labor to entrepreneurs in industry and finally, as an opportunity for entrepreneurs. Women entrepreneurial problems range from mobilizing resources including problems of capital, marketing, raw materials, sales, labor maintenance, competition from outside industries, new technologies, problems of land, water, power, taxes, lack of family support as well as lack of government support etc. Women entrepreneurs face problems which are established by the women entrepreneurship are as follows:

7.1 Financial problems

Finance is regarded as “life-blood” for any enterprise, be it big or small. However, women entrepreneurs suffer from shortage of finance on two counts. Since they are housewives, they have no source of finance at the time of introducing a new business concern. They have to borrow from outside sources like banks, financiers or industrialists.

7.2 Raw Materials

Failure of many entrepreneurial business units is decided when they are unable to get adequate number of raw materials. The prices of raw materials are quite high. This is the major problem that the women entrepreneurs face while they think of procurement of raw materials.

7.3 Competition

Women entrepreneurs face stringent competition from the outside business concerns especially from male industrialists. do not have organizational set-up to pump in a lot of money for canvassing and advertisement. Thus, they have to face a stiff competition for marketing their products with both organized sector and their male counterparts. Such a competition ultimately results in the liquidation of women enterprises.

7.4 Limited Mobility

Women entrepreneurs' area of work is highly limited in India due to various reasons. First of all they have been kept outside the business arena as they have been strongly branded as house wives. Even if they by hook or cook happen to enter the business field they have to face stiff competition within India and outside. But men are considered as born to rule the business world or otherwise.

7.5 Family Ties

In India, it is mainly a women's duty to look after the children and other members of the family. In case of married women entrepreneur, she has to possess balance between her business and family. She has to more concentrate on the business concern she is handling her total involvement in family leaves little or no energy and time to devote for business.

7.6 Lack of Education

In India, about 60% women are still illiterate. Due to the lack of education and that too qualitative education, women are hesitating to enter the business field. They are not aware of business techniques and market knowledge. Motivation among women is less when compared to men and hence they hesitate to enter the business arena. Lack of education creates many problems for women in the setting up and running of business enterprises.

7.7 Male-Dominated Society

Male domination is the salient feature of business enterprises in India. In India women are looked upon as weak in all aspects. Women suffer from male domination in areas of ability and capacity. In the male-dominated Indian society, women are not treated equal to men.

7.8 Lack of Marketing

One of the major problems faced by entrepreneurship is in the field of marketing. It has not in a position to get firsthand information about the market i.e. information about completion, taste, liking disliking of consumers. Therefore, it is not able to upgrade the products according to the changing business environment.

7.9 Lack of confidence

Women entrepreneurs exhibit a lack of self-confidence as entrepreneurs compared to men. Once in an established business, women relate to entrepreneurship less than men and do not feel comfortable calling themselves entrepreneurs. For some women, entrepreneurial self-confidence grew over their time in business.

7.10 Socio-cultural factors

Women entrepreneurs are constrained by normative factors including social dishonor or digress of women.

7.1 Low Risk-Bearing Ability

Women entrepreneurs are low risk-takers. This reduces their ability and willingness to take risks while running an enterprise. Risk-bearing is a fundamental requisite of a prosperous entrepreneur irrespective of gender

8. POLICIES AND SCHEAMS FOR WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS IN INDIA:

8.1 Schemes of Ministry of MSME

- a. Trade related entrepreneurship assistance and development (TREAD) scheme for women
- b. Mahila Coir Yojana
- c. Support to training and employment programme for women (STEP)
- d. Swayam Siddha
- e. Kerala government's women industries programme
- f. Delhi government's stree shakthi project
- g. Schemes of Delhi commission for women (related to skill development and training)
- h. Incentives to women entrepreneurs scheme, 2008, Government of Goa
- i. Magalir Udavi Scheme, Puducherry Government
- j. Financing Schemes by Banks/Financial Institutions

8. INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES:

Women in India have to take challenging roles in an Entrepreneurship. Then only they become successful in their business field. In this I would like to share my personal perspectives on Women entrepreneur.

8.1 Making Own Decisions

Most of the times women have to mingle with male industrialists and others for making own decisions. Lack of education, poverty, personal attitude towards opposite sex prevent them from interacting with business tycoons when it is really required. It is necessary for every woman to own their personality regardless of how the opposite party perceives them.

8.2 Build a support Network and Communication

Women entrepreneurs have to build a strong support system among themselves. While communicating with others sometimes women are in a dilemma to properly communicate and deciding what is to be done and what not be done.

8.3 Proper Advice

Factors like lack of education, poverty, and personal attitude towards opposite sex prevent women entrepreneurs from seeking proper advice face greater problem than men when starting businesses, especially when women meet concerned persons. For example: Professional

advisers, founders and co-founders, such as accountants and lawyers, advisory groups, mastermind groups, board of advisers, and family members.”

8.4 Delegation of Work

This system is the challenge of building a support system. Women often fear failures. Women need to understand that they need to work on their business. They have to work in a group, they have to appoint employees in certain places and proceed towards carrying their organization into a successful one.

8.5 Marketing/Advertising

Women Entrepreneur should Market or Advertise the products in a systematic way, which is useful in the present scenario. E.g.: Through Television, Face book, Whats App or any other Technological method.

8.6 Time Management

Women Entrepreneur should manage time System they have to work according to their schedule. For example: 9.00 a.m. to 6.00 p.m. or shift-wise.

8.7 Administrative Work

Women should improve their administrative skill, which is the main part in an entrepreneurship. If this is improved, there is no chance to lose the business goals.

8.8 Recruiting/Retention of Employees

Women Entrepreneurs should appoint suitable employees with the knowledge and communication skills. This will pave way for overall development of the industry in the entire entrepreneurship.

8.9 Balancing business and family life

Women entrepreneurs have dual responsibilities to their businesses and to their families. finding ways to devote time to both is key to truly achieving that elusive work-life balance, But most of the women they will manage the family and business in a systematic way. If they manage both they will become successful entrepreneur in a country.

8.10 Be involved in all segments of your start-up. Pay attention to all aspects of business — even the ones that don't interest you, “Don't delegate until you really know how to do something yourself,”

9. FOLOWING SECTORS ARE PROMOTING THE WOMEN EMPOWERMENT:

1. National Resource Centre for Women(NRCW)
2. Women's Trust India (WIT)
3. Women Development Corporation (WDC)
4. Association of Women Entrepreneurs of Karnataka (AWAKE)
5. Working Women's Forum (WWF)
6. Self Employed Women's Association (SEWA)

Fig. 2: showing the State-wise percentage of Women Entrepreneurs in India

10. SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENT:

- 1) Attitudes of the Society should be changed regarding the rigid social norms, customs, values and attitude, Awareness should be created by the Government and Non-Government Institutes through undertaking of various programmes.
- 2) Entrepreneurship courses should be introduced so that woman will Improve their Skill and Knowledge More practical and need oriented training program should be designed for entrepreneurs.
- 3) Government and financial institutions must encourage women entrepreneurs by providing low credit. As low credit ensures to promote women entrepreneurship special assistance and incentives for encouraging women entrepreneurship.
- 4) Training programs are needed for women entrepreneurs' development. Proper training shall be given to the women entrepreneurs through Government Programmes.
- 5) Many people are not aware about available entrepreneurial opportunities, though the Government is offering different types of incentives and assistance; still many people are beyond purview. There is a dire need to create awareness about entrepreneurial opportunities assistance.
- 6) There is need of Research in this area to identify the problem which is being faced by women entrepreneurs.

- 7) Women industrial estate shall be setup in each District for upgrading level of activities of women entrepreneurs.
- 8) Wide publicity should be given about the financial assistance and other incentives that are offered by the Government
- 9) Co-operative institution and Banks use a share of their profit for the promotion of women entrepreneurs by providing free training, loans with subsidy, and loan without interest for helping them to identify suitable products under their jurisdiction.
- 10) Assistance should be given in the areas like marketing, distribution, Support for selling the Output of the Women entrepreneurship products. Government assistance is needed in Annual fair and exhibitions should be arranged in regional national and international levels.
- 11) Stay inspired and motivated “Don’t be intimidated by what you don’t know. That can be your greatest strength and ensure that you do things differently from everyone else.
- 12) Acquiring knowledge is an endless process and it is vital that women are aware of the current trends and surveys to implement newer practices into their business. Ideas and solutions are spurred from attending events, seminars, workshops as awareness is created.
- 13) Family support plays a prominent role towards the success of members to inspire more confidence in the minds of women into entrepreneurship. Sessions has to be conducted by the successful women entrepreneurs so that the women will be motivated to get into entrepreneurship activity.

11. CONCLUSIONS:

Women entrepreneurs are facing many problems in a society in aspects of financial, marketing production, work place facility and health problems. Financial problems faced were non-availability of long-term finance, regular and frequent need of working capital. Poor location of shop and lack of transport facility were major marketing problems. Production problems included the problem of non-availability of raw material. Entrepreneurs also facing health problems such as tension, and headache. Women entrepreneurs also faced problem of improper water and space facility. Issues and Challenges are playing a important role to avoid these problems can help women entrepreneurs to deal with these problems effectively. Today Women Entrepreneurs are increased supportive initiatives by the Government, Families, and Support Systems.

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